

Research Article

Development and Validation of Metaxalone and Diclofenac Potassium in Bulk and Its Formulation using RP-HPLC Techniques

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ABSTRACT

This research article aims to develop and validate the Reverse-Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) technique for the simultaneous determinations of Diclofenac potassium and Metaxalone in tablets and bulk. On an Eclipse plus C₁₈ (250 mm × 4.6 mm ID, 5µm) column, chromatographic separation was accomplished with a mobile phase consisting of potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 4.2): acetonitrile (30:70 v/v) at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. The detection wavelength was selected to be 280 nm. Diclofenac potassium and Metaxalone were shown to have retention periods of 4.60 and 3.25 minutes, respectively. As per ICH Q₂(R₁) requirements, the proposed technique was validated using metrics such as linearity, accuracy, system suitability, precision, and robustness. Diclofenac potassium and Metaxalone in tablet dosage forms were determined quantitatively using the established and verified technique.

INTRODUCTION

Diclofenac potassium (DICLO) exerts its anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, and analgesic effects by blocking prostaglandin production via cyclooxygenase (COX). By preventing bacterial DNA synthesis, it also seems to have bacteriostatic properties. Diclofenac potassium is chemically 2-[2-(2,6-dichloroanilino) phenyl] acetate, with a molecular mass of 334.2 g/mol and the molecular formula C₁₄H₁₀C₁₂KNO₂.^{1,2}

Metaxalone helps to reduce pain from injury and other muscular-skeletal disorders by relaxing muscles.¹ The precise mechanism of action of metaxalone in humans is unclear, however, it may be associated with a widespread central nervous system depression. It has no direct impact on the motor end plate, nerve fiber, or striated muscle's contractile mechanism. The liver breaks down metaxalone, which is then eliminated in the urine as unknown metabolites.^{3,4} The IUPAC name of

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Metaxalone is 5- [(3, 5-dimethyl phenoxy) methyl]-1,3-oxazolidin-2-one with molecular formula $C_{12}H_{15}NO_3$ and molecular mass 221.25 g/mol.¹ According to the literature survey, fewer RP-HPLC techniques have been documented to estimate these drugs both alone and in combination in pharmaceutical dosage forms. Other analytical techniques, including UV^{5,6}, HPLC^{7,8}, LCMS⁹, HPTLC³, RP-UPLC¹⁰, and stability-indicating RP-HPLC¹¹, have also been reported.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials:

A standard Diclofenac Potassium and Metaxalone were obtained from Micro Lab Mumbai as a gift sample. While Diclofenac Potassium and Metaxalone Tablets purchase from local market. Were as Acetonitrile, Potassium dihydrogen phosphate, and Orthophosphoric acid from Merk Laboratories Mumbai.

Instrument:

Table: 1 Instrument and Equipment used for the Analytical Method Development and Validation studies

Sr No.	Name of Instruments	Make and Model
1.	HPLC Software	Agilent Technology Ezchrome
2.	UV-Vis Spectrophotometer Software	Shimadzu UV-1800 UV probe
3.	Ultra sonicator	Life Care Equipment
4.	Electronic Weighing Balance	Shimadzu (sensitivity 0.001 gm)

Methods

Preparation of Phosphate Buffer

Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate (2.72 g) was precisely weighed and diluted in 1000 millilitres of HPLC-grade water. Before being sonicated, the pH was adjusted to 4.2 using orthophosphoric acid.

Preparation of standard stock solution

a) Diclofenac Potassium

100 mg of Diclofenac potassium was precisely weighed and transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask, diluting it with acetonitrile, and then sonicating it to the proper strength, resulting in a concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Acetonitrile was used to dilute 10 mL of the above standard stock solution to the necessary concentration in a 100 mL volumetric flask, resulting in a sub-stock solution with a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

b) Metaxalone

100 mg of Metaxalone was precisely weighed and transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask, diluting it with acetonitrile, and then sonicating it to the proper strength, resulting in a concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Acetonitrile was used to dilute 10 mL of the above standard stock solution to the necessary concentration in a 100 mL volumetric flask, resulting in a sub-stock solution with a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Preparation of sample stock solution

a) Diclofenac Potassium

Twenty tablets were carefully weighed and crushed into a fine powder. In a volumetric flask with a total volume of 100 mL, a volume equal to 100 mg was obtained, transferred, diluted with acetonitrile, and sonicated for 15 minutes. Whatman No. 1 filter paper was used to filter this mixture. 1 mL of the previously described sample stock solution was put into a 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted with acetonitrile to create the solution with a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

b) Metaxalone

Twenty tablets were carefully weighed and crushed into a fine powder. In a volumetric flask with a total volume of 100 mL, a volume equal to 100 mg was obtained, transferred, diluted with acetonitrile, and sonicated for 15 minutes. Whatman No. 1 filter paper was used to filter this mixture. 1 mL of the previously described sample stock solution was put into a 10 mL volumetric

flask and diluted with acetonitrile to create the solution with a concentration of 100 µg/mL.

Method Development

Trial 1

Column Used: Eclipse plus C₁₈ (250 mm × 4.6 mm ID, 5µm)

Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile: Water (50:50)

Flow rate: 1 ml/min

Wavelength: 280 nm

Temperature: 30°C

Fig. 1 Chromatogram for Acetonitrile: Water (50:50)

Fig. 2 Chromatogram for Acetonitrile: Water (50:50)

Trial 2

Column Used: Eclipse plus C₁₈ (250 mm × 4.6 mm ID, 5µm)

Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile: Methanol (60:40)

Flow rate: 1 ml/min

Wavelength: 280 nm

Temperature: 30°C

Fig. 3 Chromatogram for Acetonitrile: Methanol (60:40)

Fig: 4 Chromatogram for Acetonitrile: Methanol (60:40)

Optimized Method:

Drugs were eluted with a good retention time, and all system parameters, including tailing factors and plate count, were within acceptable limits.
 Column Used: Eclipse plus C₁₈ (250 mm × 4.6 mm ID, 5µm)

Mobile Phase: Phosphate Buffer (pH 4.2): Acetonitrile (30:70)
 Flow rate: 1 ml/min
 Wavelength: 280 nm
 Temperature: 30°C

Fig: 5 Chromatogram for Phosphate Buffer (pH 4.2): Acetonitrile (30:70)

Fig: 6 Chromatogram for Phosphate Buffer (pH 4.2): Acetonitrile (30:70)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1) System suitability: According to ICH criteria, every system suitability parameter is within the acceptable range.

Table: 2 System suitability studies of Diclofenac Potassium and Metaxalone

Property	Diclofenac Potassium	Metaxalone
Retention Time	4.60	3.25
Theoretical plates	3346	3280
Tailing Fctor	1.3	1.3

Fig: 7 Optimized Chromatogram of Metaxalone and Diclofenac Potassium

2) **Linearity:** A series of dilutions were made using the standard stock solution to evaluate the linearity of the medication Diclofenac Potassium and Metaxalone. The linearity range was 5–30 µg/mL.

1	5	437252
2	10	828057
3	15	1175853
4	20	1584237
5	25	2022356
6	30	2450232

a) **Diclofenac Potassium**

Table: 3 Calibration data for Diclofenac Potassium

Sr No.	Concentration	Peak area
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Fig: 8 Calibration Curve of Diclofenac Potassium

Fig: 9 Typical Chromatogram of Diclofenac Potassium

b) Metaxalone**Table: 4 Calibration data for Diclofenac Potassium**

Sr No.	Concentration	Peak area
1	5	56359
2	10	106699
3	15	157035
4	20	213524
5	25	259626
6	30	322515

Fig: 11 Typical Chromatogram of Metaxalone**3) Precision**

The intraday (Repeatability was tested by evaluating a standard solution on same day.) and inter-day (Repeatability was tested by evaluating a standard solution on three days.) methods were

used to measure precision. To do precise examination, six injections of standard solutions were produced. Results are expressed as %RSD.

Table: 5 Intraday and Interday Precision data for Diclofenac Potassium

Sr No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Intraday Precision	Interday Precision
1	20	1584237	1560338
2	20	1583421	1560636

3	20	1608324	1559403
4	20	1587156	1559130
5	20	1583183	1557802
6	20	1582648	1516629
Mean		1588162	1552323
SD		10005.95	17515.07
% RSD		0.63	1.13

Table: 6 Intraday and Interday Precision data for Metaxalone

Sr No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Intraday Precision	Interday Precision
1	20	210504	204971
2	20	210761	204786
3	20	210761	204894
4	20	210768	204903
5	20	210846	205008
6	20	210414	204898
Mean		210676	204910
SD		173.23	76.35
% RSD		0.08	0.04

Fig:12 Chromatogram of Diclofenac Potassium for intraday precision

Fig:13 Chromatogram of Diclofenac Potassium for interday precision

Fig:14 Chromatogram of Metaxalone for intraday precision

Fig:15 Chromatogram of Metaxalone for interday precision

4) Accuracy

Three distinct concentrations of the drug's percentage accuracy are 80%, 100%, and 120%.

The mean recovery percentage was then calculated based on the results obtained from the recovery studies.

Table: 7 Accuracy data of Diclofenac Potassium and Metaxalone

Sample	Concentration (%) (µg/ml)	Amount Recovered (µg/ml)	Recovery (%)	%RSD
Diclofenac Potassium	18	17.69	98.30	0.25
	20	20.32	98.01	0.02
	22	22.06	100.31	0.10
Metaxalone	18	18.07	100.40	0.01
	20	20.09	100.46	0.08
	22	21.70	98.62	0.06

Fig:16 Chromatogram of Diclofenac Potassium for accuracy at 80%

Fig:17 Chromatogram of Diclofenac Potassium for accuracy at 100%

Fig:18 Chromatogram of Diclofenac Potassium for accuracy at 120%

Fig:19 Chromatogram of Metaxalone for accuracy at 80%

Fig: 20 Chromatogram of Diclofenac Potassium for accuracy at 100%

Fig: 21 Chromatogram of Metaxalone for accuracy at 120%

5) Robustness

Small deliberate adjustments were made to the flow rate, temperature, and wavelength, but the

results were within the ICH standards and showed no significant variation.

a) Diclofenac Potassium

Table: 8 Robustness data of Diclofenac Potassium

Sr No.		1	2	3	Mean	SD	%RSD	
Flow Rate	1.2ml/min	AREA	1486674	1487124	1486878	1486892	225.33	0.02
		RT	4.15	4.15	4.15	4	0.00	0.00
		NTP	3345	3371	3378	3365	17.39	0.52
	0.8ml/min	AREA	1866173	1866318	1867928	1866806	974.09	0.05
		RT	5.09	5.09	5.09	5	0.00	0.00
		NTP	3372	3358	3344	3358	14.00	0.42
Temp	20°C	AREA	1848748	1851497	1854070	1851438	2661.48	0.14
		RT	4.6	4.6	4.59	5	0.01	0.13
		NTP	3339	3300	3327	3322	19.97	0.60
	30°C	AREA	1609730	1617870	1622416	1616672	6427.29	0.40
		RT	4.17	4.16	4.17	4	0.01	0.14
		NTP	3357	3348	3365	3357	8.50	0.25
Wavelength	278	AREA	1605532	1606245	1613456	1608411	4383.62	0.27
		RT	4.5	4.5	4.51	5	0.01	0.13
		NTP	3277	3254	3227	3253	25.03	0.77
	282	AREA	1607560	1606033	1606045	1606546	878.17	0.05
		RT	4.56	4.55	4.55	5	0.01	0.13
		NTP	3248	3297	3260	3268	25.54	0.78

b) Metaxalone

Table: 9 Robustness data of Metaxalone

Sr No.		1	2	3	Mean	SD	%RSD	
Flow rate	1.2ml/min	AREA	197212	197689	197852	197584	332.59	0.17
		RT	2.97	2.97	2.97	3	0.00	0.00
		NTP	3374	3376	3388	3379	7.57	0.22
	0.8ml/min	AREA	239795	240904	240859	240519	627.69	0.26
		RT	3.63	3.63	3.63	4	0.00	0.00
		NTP	3452	3440	3439	3444	7.23	0.21
Temp	20°C	AREA	213429	213767	214440	213879	514.67	0.24
		RT	3.25	3.25	3.25	3	0.00	0.00
		NTP	3374	3352	3377	3368	13.65	0.41
	30°C	AREA	198741	199283	199595	199206	432.13	0.22
		RT	3.1	3.1	3.12	3	0.01	0.37
		NTP	3357	3348	3365	3357	8.50	0.25
Wavelength	278	AREA	231172	231782	232154	231703	495.78	0.21
		RT	3.27	3.27	3.27	3	0.00	0.00
		NTP	3301	3287	3265	3284	18.15	0.55
	282	AREA	198654	198632	198564	198617	46.92	0.02
		RT	3.27	3.27	3.27	3	0.00	0.00
		NTP	3296	3282	3268	3282	14.00	0.43

6) Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

a) Diclofenac Potassium

LOD for Diclofenac Potassium was 0.5169 µg/ml.

LOQ for Diclofenac Potassium was 1.5665 µg/ml.

b) Metaxalone

LOD for Metaxalone was 0.47856µg/ml.

LOQ for Metaxalone was 1.45019 µg/ml.

CONCLUSION

A simple, rapid, selective, and accurate RP-HPLC technique has been developed to assess Diclofenac Potassium and Metaxalone in bulk medications and formulations. The mobile phase was Phosphate buffer (pH 4.2): Acetonitrile (30:70). The flow rate was 1.0 ml/min and an injection volume of 20 µL. The retention times of diclofenac potassium and metaxalone were found to be 4.60 and 3.25 minutes, respectively. The linearity, precision, accuracy (recovery), robustness, and filter appropriateness of this approach were all validated and determined to be within the given range.

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